

LIVED EXPERIENCES OF HOSPITALITY MANAGEMENT TRAINEES OF TRAVEL PROGRAM IN THE UNITED STATES OF AMERICA: A PHENOMENOLOGICAL STUDY

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Abstract

Hospitality and tourism professionals expect university graduates to have jobs that meet industry expectations. Universities have long incorporated foreign placements to develop student competencies and bridge the gap between theoretical experience and industry practice to meet the hospitality industry's standards (Sasam et al., 2015). This study aimed to learn more about hospitality management students' lived experiences in the Student Cultural Exchange and Travel Program (SCETP) in the United States during their international on-the-job training (OJT). The study will follow the descriptive phenomenology in the qualitative research approach utilizing Colaizzi's method, which drew from the experiential learning theory of John Dewey 1938 (Roberts, T. G. 2003). After a one-on-one thorough interview and analysis of a transcribed audio recording of participants, it was observed that there was a common experience during their On-the-Job Training. Moreover, the study revealed that in the experiences of students in their on-the-job training in the USA, seven emergent themes have emerged: these are cultural and environment adjustment; challenges; and family-oriented. For the coping mechanism: focused at work; learned to speak the language, and family is the strength. And for the piece of advice: experiential learning. Each theme was quoted by the participants and was carefully discussed and interpreted by the researchers. The study will serve as the framework for strengthening the internship coordinator's monitoring system and quality of education.

Keywords: hospitality management trainee, on-the-job training, phenomenology, Philippines.

1. INTRODUCTION

Nations are rapidly evolving and becoming increasingly reliant on one another for products and services in today's highly globalized world. Business around the world competes in a world with few national borders and restrictions.

The word "globalization" refers to the growth of global trade and the increased interconnectedness of nations and markets. (Achterberg, 2003).

The importance of hospitality education in the development of the industry is crucial to the industry's evolution. From the 1920s, when Cornell University developed the first hospitality management program, today, when there are more than 200 four-year institutions training students for careers in the hospitality industry, specialized hospitality management programs have been around for a long time (Annaraud, 2006). Since the 1920s, hospitality educators have looked to industry leaders to guide graduates'

essential competencies for success (Kay & Russette, 2000), and hospitality management programs have changed significantly to meet the industry's perceived changing needs (Pavesic, 1991). By incorporating experiential learning standards into the academic curriculum, these activities have started to play a role in developing many of students' desired competencies. Internships, service learning, and practicums are all examples of experiential learning that are thought to be essential components of sound business education (Quantilla Anderson-Noto & Paul Watkins, 2013)

Internships, placements, and practicums in higher education are all words for a period of jobs in the tourism and hospitality industry. Job experience and cooperative education are two other concepts (Busby, 2003; Inui, Wheeler & Lankford, 2006; Leslie & Richardson, 2000; Waryszak, 1997). Internships can last as little as four weeks or as long as a year and a half (Busby, Brunt, & Baber, 1997), and they can be domestic or foreign (Busby, Brunt, & Baber, 1997). They can serve as a link between academics and industry (Airey & Johnson, 1999; Busby et al., 1997). Some industries prefer interns with a tourism or hospitality degree (Busby, 2001), undoubtedly providing crucial commercial knowledge.

Internships in academia are described as "an opportunity to incorporate the work-related experience into graduate education by engaging in scheduled and supervised work" (Gault et al., 2010). In this study, the term internship is used solely to refer to undergraduate students undergoing academic internships. Internships provide students with real-world work experience, allowing them to acquire practical knowledge and experiences and the generic and specialized skills needed to jumpstart their professional careers (Gerken et al., 2012). Prior research has also shown that internships improve students' academic and professional performance (Knouse et al., 1999). Internships enable students to put what they've learned in class into practice, gain a broad understanding of industry requirements, and test career choices by providing students with realistic expectations on the field as a whole (Barron, 1999; Barron and Maxwell, 1993; Emenheiser et al., as cited by Walo, 2001; Petrillose and Montgomery, 1998).

Internships are critical in bridging the gap between theory and experience in their fieldwork. In essence, an educational practicum is a supervised on-site work experience that allows students to practice and demonstrate their growing skills and competencies in their chosen profession (Armada, M. & Armada, A. 2021). These are hands-on learning opportunities that encourage students to observe and record how working professionals carry out their duties. Students will also conduct activities under program professors' direction and an on-site supervisor to a minimal degree.

Students would lack the capacity and experiences to relate to others in the world they live and work in if they did not acquire a global competency (Achterberg, 2003). In this text, global competency refers to one's ability to empathize with and approve of other people's forms of life, as well as one's ability to interact effectively across cultures (Hunter, 2004). To be prepared for their futures after graduation, students must know various cultures, political structures, and communities (Morey, 2000). In our evolving

world, it is crucial to foster international awareness and a global outlook among college students (Achterberg, 2003) to provide students with the skills they will need to be effective in the workplace and life.

Noe, Hollenback, Gerhart, & Wright, (2011) posited that one type of experiential education is internships and practicum. On-the-job training (OJT) is a type of training in which a person with prior work experience and knowledge assists trainees in practicing job skills on the job. Apprenticeships and internships are two examples of this type of training. The sponsoring institution collaborates with local and international firms to place students in employment that allow them to get relevant experience in their field of study.

UN, L. B. (2014) reported that experiential Education and Internship Programs have varied through local worldwide ties with business and the business setting. It has also created the path for universities and colleges to form contractual agreements within the country and abroad to strengthen every Filipino's expertise and make them globally competitive in the workplace

On the other hand Kaufmann, Martin, Weaver & Weaver, (1992) postulated that on-the-job training abroad is one way for students to acquire the skills they need to work in the current global world. Students learn about their own culture and have the ability to become knowledgeable, if not proficient, in another culture after participating in a study abroad program. Training in a foreign country helps students see America from a tourist's eyes, giving them a new perspective (Hansen, 2002). One advantage of training abroad for students with cultural apathy is becoming less insensitive to diversity and other cultures. A greater understanding of different cultures and the differences that they represent.

Thus, this paper primarily aimed to find out the the learning experiences of student interns of Eastern Visayas State University in program of Hospitality Management during their international on-the-job training (OJT) in the United States of America.

2. REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Interning abroad is a cross-cultural study of education that looks at the effect of culture on individual learning styles and the variations in learning techniques between people in different cultures (Exposito 2015). The use of concepts like integrated learning and work-based learning, which they see as umbrella terms to encompass a wide variety of educational experiences that include formal higher education and workplace experience, has been noted by Garner and Bartkus (2014). There was also some ambiguity in terminology used to characterize higher education institution programs that include such work experiences. Internships were often confused with words like externships (Freeley 2006), internship practicums (Bay, 2006), and cooperative internships, according to Garner and Bartkus (2014).

2.1 Work based on the job training

On-the-job training is a form of cooperative education that benefits both the student and the businesses and educational institutions that participate. Hartley & Theil are a law firm based in London (1997). These programs provide interns with opportunities to gain work experience, explore relationships with organizations that may provide potential job opportunities and growth, form networks, and improve interpersonal skills outside of a formal educational environment. Partnerships with students and higher education institutions provide public relations opportunities, lift company profiles, and provide possible new labor and knowledge transfer for participating businesses. Internships give ties to the real world of work for H.E.I.s, as well as the ability to apply management theory in practice, while also growing institutional appeal for new students and improving the reputation and even status of an institution (Thiel & Hartley, 1997; Coco, 2000; Gault et al., 2000; Knemeyer & Murphy, 2002; Weible, 2010).

2.2 Internationalization of the management curriculum

Educators and business planners speculated at the turn of the 20th century that the future world of work would provide increasingly valuable prospects for those skilled in intercultural communication and cross-cultural leadership (Adler, 1998; Barnlund, 1998; Bennett, 1998; Harris & Moran, 1996). Higher education institutions have long sought ways to internationalize their curricula to varying degrees to meet such business futurists' aspirations (Ryan 2005, Wilkinson, 2006). Immersive international learning for students is one approach that higher education professionals often cite as a potentially successful way to bring a level of internationalization to higher education. The best way for students to gain more exposure and opportunities to study abroad is to engage in foreign experiences.

Jane Knight (2016) defines internalization of higher education as the process of integrating an international or intercultural dimension into the teaching, research, and service functions of the institution, and she defines internationalization of higher education as the process of integrating an international or intercultural dimension into the teaching, research, and service functions of the institution. Knight previously stated that "internationalization is a dynamic process, not a collection of isolated activities, but a process of integration or infusion that contributes to the sustainability of the international dimension, as well as the primary and universal functions of a higher education institution, namely teaching, research, and service to society," in her earlier writings. (Un, L. B. 2014).

(Knight, J. & De Wit, H. 1997) posited that internationalization can also be seen in the graduates of a given institution's socio-cultural competence. The function of internationalization in promoting cultural and ethnic variety in the academic world is the cultural and social motivation for higher education globalization

Likewise, according to (Aguinaldo Matriano, E. D. 2017) many hospitality curricula incorporate some form of industry-based experiential learning to complement the classroom environment. Many of these previously documented benefits of experiential

learning and identified new learning outcomes or benefits for students who participate in experiential learning, such as an increased understanding of how organizations function, increased ability to view career expectations realistically, an increased network of professional contacts, increased ability to take initiative, increased.

2.3 Benefits of on-the-job training in abroad

Most notably, they highlight a void in the literature about students' perceptions of international learning programs' importance and significance. Following a systematic study of internship stakeholder studies, Sanahuja-Vélez and Ribes-Giner (2015) concluded that the beneficial results of business internships were a win-win situation for the three key stakeholders: students, employers, and higher education institutions. According to Ortiz (2004: 264), international internships are a strategic necessity for universities because they "provide a well-rounded education by allowing participating business students to obtain international exposure." According to Oritz, such exposure would allow for contact with international peers and managers, allowing for the growth of "global competency."

2.4 Benefits for Students

According to Glätzle and Seppälä-Esser (2017), students' programs' possible advantages are illustrated by addressing universities' challenges in coordinating and hiring students for international work experience programs. Personal growth is accomplished by getting the ability to work in a new working and social setting and by developing language skills. Students will learn to think globally, become more versatile, and achieve independence by learning to adapt to a new environment. These are the characteristics that prospective employers are constantly looking for in their workers. Gaining language skills, which was once thought to be the primary goal of on-the-job preparation, is now an essential part of a student's educational success in a foreign country. Students who received on-the-job training in non-English speaking countries developed their foreign language skills (Cummings, 2001). According to many experts, language learning is an essential advantage in educational achievement for on-the-job preparation. Students have claimed that the crucial part of their study abroad experience is the language skills they have acquired (Kaufmann et al., 1992). Students, who are an essential part of the educational process, can benefit from reviewing this report's results. Exposure to themes that emerge from peers' lived experiences can aid in uniting and motivating a collective student voice in the organizational process. The value of student's voices in higher education cannot be overstated. According to research, students bear the most responsibility for evaluating the effect of people, programs, facilities, and activities on their university experience (Pascarella & Terenzini, 2005).

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Design

The thematic analysis of Colaizzi technique (1978) for descriptive phenomenology was used in this descriptive qualitative analysis (Sanders, 2003). Descriptive phenomenology is a research philosophy that uses human lived experience to evoke facts (Polit and Beck, 2008; Speziale and Carpenter, 2007). According to Laverly (2003), phenomenology is concerned with the world as perceived by an individual rather than the world reality.

This study aimed to learn more about hospitality management students' lived experiences in the Student Cultural Exchange and Travel Abroad Program (SCETP) in the United States. The study will follow the descriptive phenomenology in the qualitative research approach utilizing Colaizzi's method, which drew from experiential learning theory.

3.2 Sampling

In this study, purposive sampling was used to select participants who were deemed able to provide the best information and contribute to understanding the research problem (Creswell, 2013).

Since the program fee is too expensive, not all students can afford to pay a considerable amount to do On-the-job training in America. Only four (4) trainees purposefully selected for this study because they are the only 4th year students who can afford the program fee and completed the Student Cultural Exchange and Travel Program (SCETP) in the United States of America.

3.3. Research Participants

There were only four (4) participants in this study. Who are 4th-year college students taking up Bachelor of Science in Hospitality Management Program? They are the only 4th year students who can afford to pay in the program fee and completed the on-the-job training in the United States of America. Other OJT's who cannot afford to pay the program fee are deployed with industry partners in the Philippines.

3.4 Data Collection Procedure

According to Gill, P., Stewart, K., Treasure, E., & Chadwick, B. (2008). When preparing an interview schedule, it's essential to ask questions that will yield as much knowledge about the study phenomenon as possible while still discussing the research's goals and objectives. Good questions for a qualitative interview should be open-ended (requiring more than a yes/no response), neutral, sensitive, and understandable.

To extract information from the participants, we conducted a semi-structured face-to-face interview. With the participants' permission, we used an audio recorder to ensure that everything was captured. We ended the discussion with the participants after collecting all of the necessary information through probing questions.

3.5 Data Analysis Procedure

Data analysis should start simultaneously as data collection in qualitative studies (Creswell, 2003, 2009; Speziale and Carpenter, 2007). Semi-structured, face-to-face interviews were conducted using a pre-prepared interview guide. Participants were encouraged to talk freely and to tell stories using their own words. All transcript is translated and transcribed into the English language. The following measures were used to carry out Colaizzi's (1978) phenomenological data analysis approach. The first approach is to read and re-read transcripts more than a few times to understand the full content to use data. The significant statements related to hospitality management trainees' lived experiences of travel programs in the United States of America were then extracted from each transcript. The extracted significant statements should be transferred in another sheet to cluster each statement. After separating and listing the statement, the researcher created the formulated meanings from these significant statements (Shosha, G. A. 2012). The formulated meanings were grouped into groups, theme clusters and theme (Sanders, 2002). Many of the themes that arose were examined to see whether they were internally convergent and externally divergent (Mason, 2002; Silverman, 2005). The final step included describing the emerging themes as well as the phenomenon's basic structure.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results are presented and discussed using a linear framework that includes the research question, theme, meaning, and evidence (Adu, 2019). The objectives are highlighted in the presentation: the first statement of the problem is hospitality professionals' experiences in their on-the-job training; and the coping techniques used in their on-the-job training issues.

The themes are presented, and the quotes from the participants are utilized to emphasize the experience of the participants on the particular theme. While the theme is presented, experiences among the participants will transpire.

4.1 On the experiences of hospitality professionals during their on-the-job training

4.1.1 Theme 1: Cultural and Environment Adjustment

4.1.2 Meaning:

Culture is a set of shared beliefs, ideas, attitudes, and customs passed down from generation to generation in society. Because Filipinos are known for their hospitality, adjusting to other ethnicity and appreciating their culture is not difficult.

This theme validates the claim of Luo, Y. (2016) that reverse adaptation refers to the case where employees learn, assimilate, and modify their behavior (e.g., values, norms) and professional competence (e.g., standards, goals, language, knowledge, capability) in contrast to local adaptation, which focuses on foreign multinationals learning about

and adapting to local (host country) culture and environment. Furthermore, fostering and transforming talent into global talent needs efforts on various levels, including cultural, professional, structural, informational, and organizational, from different individual levels.

4.1.3 Evidence:

According to MP4, the OJT experience is unique since they encountered various nationalities, but they could adjust and work with them without difficulty:

“An culture ngadto kakaiba hiya kay it tawo ha USA Kay grabe nira ka out spoken kun ano it ira gusto iyakan ig yayakan gud talaga nira straight to the point gud Hira waray paligoy-ligoy, oo dirediretso talaga Hira prangka nga kuan kun ano an ira kuan Baga malain nga kuan ig yayakan gud nira ha imo” (MP4, Transcript 48, page 10, line 360-364).

(“The culture is different because Americans are very outspoken about what they want to say. They are straight to the point no matter how bad it is”)

Likewise, MP2 also experienced a culture shock in their On-the-job training abroad.

“Na culture shock din ako dahil iba talaga doon, busy masyado an tao don sa America trabaho-trabaho sila doon halos lahat ng oras hindi gaya dito sa pilipinas maraming okasyon (MP2, Transcript 25, page 4, line 146-148).

(“I'm also a culture shock because it's different there, people are very busy in America, they work there most of the time, unlike here in the Philippines, and there are many occasions)

Meanwhile, some of the participants they experience the strange climate in America that is really very cold weather. MP1 highlighted that:

“Na experience ko doon yung napakalamig talaga ang hirap maglakad minsan dahil wala ka naming masakyan di gaya dito sa atin sa pilipinas pwedi ka maki hits pag nakakita ka ng sasakyan”

(MP1, Transcript 9, page 2, line 48-51).

(“I experienced there that it's freezing, it's hard to walk sometimes because we don't have you to ride, unlike here in the Philippines. You can get hit when you see a car.”)

MP2 also reiterated that:

Sa klima naman nakakapanibago dahil talagang napakalamig sa America kailangan doble ang suot ko para hindi ako lamigin talagang nakakapanginig ng katawan sa lamig. (MP2, Transcript 28, page 4, line 156-158).

(The climate is different because it's freezing in America. I have to wear twice as much to don't get cold, making my body shiver in the cold.)

The Participants also reported that they experience a language barrier; they have difficulty in understanding the Spanish language because most of the workers in America are Mexican, although they are Mexican, they can work with them with harmonious relationships. MP3 says:

“Kay tungod man it iya niyaknan ngadto kay Spanish baga

nakuriaan anay ako makaintindi diri man gud hira nagi english kay diri man Americano it amon mga katrabaho puro man Mexican” (MP3, Transcript 38, page 7, line 253-255).

(Their language is Spanish, it's difficult for me to understand them because they can't speak english very well. After all, our co-workers are not American and are all Mexican.”)

MP4 also reported that:

“Buutan man gud an akon mga katrabaho ha hotel an usa ko la nga nakurian is an language barrier kasi kuan nag expect kami tanan nga tawo ngadto nag- eenglish so siguro ha Amon la adto Kay Spanish kasi an usually nga language an ginagamit nira pero in all okey man Hira Spanish”(MP4, Transcript 47, page 9, line 347-351).

(“My co-workers at the hotel are also very kind. The only thing I have noticed is the language barrier because we all expect people to speak English. Maybe it's only for us because usually they used the Spanish language. But they are good.)

4.1.4 Theme 2: Challenges

4.1.5 Meaning:

We find it challenging to describe learning to work hard in our own words; based on the participants' different stories, learning to work hard is considered more important; you learn to work no matter how hard it is because you have a dream.

Moreover in the study conducted by Velo, V. and Mittaz, C. (2006) that essential skills of educators in hospitality management should develop to generate professionals who are mentally ready to confront present and future challenges

4.1.6 Evidence:

Willing to work hard to set things right, no matter how difficult the job is, you are still ready to learn. MP3 mention that:

“Talagang makuri an trabaho nahibaro nala ako maka pag adjust an akon mga buruhaton kay kailangan ko man humanon kay kun diri ako man la guihapon it matrabaho ito kay akon man ito task nga assignment” (MP3, Transcript 35, page 6, line 229-232).

(“The work was hard knowing I could adjust my tasks because I have to finish my work, if not I am still the one to do my task assignment.)

Similarly to other participants, it wasn't easy, but they able to learn, MP1 also reported that:

“Super ganda sa amerika kung bibigyan pa ako ng pagkakataon makabalik mas gugustuhin kong makabalik at makatrabaho ng America. Marami akong natutunan parti sa trabaho, medyo mahirap ng una pero sa kalaunan natutu rin naman”(MP1, Transcript 5, page 1, line 32-35).

(“It's super nice in America if I am given another chance to come back I would rather be able to come back and work in America. I learned a lot at work, it was a bit difficult at first, but later I knew as well)

On the other hand, MP1 reported that:

“Sa pilipinas po kase parang wala po akong pakialam sa oras, pero ng makapag ojt ako ng America natutunan ko ang kahalagahan ng oras, lahat ng dadaang minuto importante lahat. Hindi pwedi mamaya na or bukas nalang” (MP1, Transcript 12, page 2, line 69-72).

(“In the Philippines, I don't seem to care about time, but when I got to America, I learned the importance of time; every passing minute is important. It can't be later or tomorrow.”)

Meanwhile, MP3 believed that:

“Nabaro ako hin disiplina ha America importante gud an oras ngadto, time management man gud it akon baga nakuha nabaruan, nabaro guihap ako parti hin mga technique ha trabaho nga didto ko la naadman kay ha school basic man gud la” (MP3, Transcript 39, page 7, line 266-269).

(“I learned a discipline in America that time is significant, time management is also something I've learned, I've learned a lot about the techniques at work that I only learned there than in basic school.”)

Further, Participants also indicated that they learned to become independent in life and them able to boost their self-confidence MP1 says:

“At naging independente rin ako nasanay ako na malayo sa pamilya”

(MP1, Transcript 13, page 2, line 78-79).

(“And I also became independent. I got used to being away from family.”)

In the same manner MP4 pointed out that:

“Naboost an amon confidence syempre lalo na pagmag-apply kana magagamitan experience nimo nakagtrabaho ka ha USA sugad hito” (MP4, Transcript 50, page 10, line 387-389).

(“Our confidence is boosted, especially when you apply in the industry you will use the experience you have in the USA.”)

MP3 viewed and says:

“Nagka may ada ako self-confidence pag atubang ha tawo diri na ako awdunon parehas han una” (MP3, Transcript 40, page 7, line 269-271).

("I have more self-confidence in front of people; I'm not as shy as before.")

4.1.7 Theme 3: Family Oriented

4.1.8 Meaning:

One of the most important cultural values in the societies is family-oriented collectivism (Li, J., Khatri, N. and Lam, K. 1999). In the same manner (Scarlet 2021) pointed out that many people seem to live by the phrase "family first". We all want to spend more time with our families and be present for special occasions such as family night dinners, but work and other obligations can make this difficult at times. To be a family-oriented person, why it's vital, and how to become more focused on your loved ones. A family-oriented person never loses sight of the importance of their loved ones. They may be called away from time to time due to other obligations. They will, however, always prioritize keeping a strong presence in their family.

4.1.9 Evidence:

One of the participants pointed out that when they are in abroad, they feel homesick when they arrived. He wanted to go home, but he realized that they only stay in a short while. MP1 says:

“Nanibago ako nung una nakaka home sick gusto kung umuwi pero na realize ko na kailangan ko tapusin ang OJT ko at isa pa saglit lang naman ka mi dito sa America” (MP1, Transcript 3, page 1, line 27-29).

("I feel home-sick and wanted to go home, but then I realized that I had to finish my OJT, and we were here in America for the moment.)

Furthermore, MP2 reiterated that:

An una mauli uli gad naabat ako hin home sick waray ko masyado kaistorya. (MP2, Transcript 24, page 4, line 144-148).

(At first I want to go home, I feel homesick and can't talk to anyone)

(Scarlet 2021) postulated that a person that is family oriented never forgets how important their family is. Yes, they may be called away from time to time due to other obligations. He or she will, however, always prioritize keeping a strong presence in their family.

4.2 On coping strategies employed in addressing the challenges encountered

4.2.1 Theme 1: Focused at Work

4.2.2 Meaning:

Braganza, N. (2020), identified the concept of a "work focus" recognizes that abilities and interests vary throughout time. There may be occasions when you need to upskill or discover that you want to learn a new skill. R. Fluegge-Woolf, E. (2014) also viewed that workplace enjoyment is found to be favorably and directly associated with organizational citizenship behavior and positively and indirectly to task and creative performance. Furthermore, those who enjoy themselves at work are more likely to be interested in their work and, as a result, perform better creatively.

4.2.3 Evidence:

MP1 mention that when he experience many challenges in the workplace, what he did is just focused on work. And says:

“Maramin po akong expereinece na challenges, gaya po pag kakaramdam ako ng homesick ginagawa ko nalang is focus sa trabaho, isa pa para din naman sa akin ito para may matutunan ako” (MP1, Transcript 16, page 2, line 87-89).

("I have experienced many challenges, like when I feel homesick, and I just focus on work; it's also for me so I can learn something.")

In the same manner MP2 pointed out that he just focused on work when he also experience challenges in his on-the-job training abroad.

“Noong naka feel ako po han homesick nag focus lang ako sa ojt para mawara an homesickness atleast nalilibang ako an akon trabaho. (MP2, Transcript 29, page 4, line 167-168).

("When I felt homesick, I just focused on on-the-job training to get rid of homesickness; at least I enjoyed my work.)

MP1 also reported that when he experience problem with the customers, he tries to solve the problem and ignored it.

“Pagnakaka experience ako ng problema sa customer hindi ko nalng pinapansin pero I try my best na ma solve yung problem nandiyan naman yung supervisor naming pag talagang iba na ang sitwasyon.” (MP1, Transcript 17, page 2-3, line 90-93).

("When I experience a customer problem, I ignore them, but I try my best to solve the problem; our supervisor is there when the situation is different.")

To stay focus on your work, you have to remove anything in your environment that could cause disruptions, you will be more productive and have a higher chance of staying focused (Indeed Editorial Team, 2021).

4.2.4 Theme 2: Learned to Speak the Language

4.2.5 Meaning:

Every community's brain and heart is language. You must communicate in their language if you want to become a part of another culture and merge with people on the other side of the globe; otherwise, you will not comprehend their lives and always be strangers. Invest time in studying a foreign language if you want to live or feel at ease wherever. You can learn a language on your own if you have the right motivation (On my canvass, 2021).

4.2.6 Evidence:

MP2 has found that they have difficulty in language because their co-workers are Spanish, and they speak Spanish dialect with a combination of a little English and signed language communication. Although there are speaking Spanish, they will be able to adjust and learn to speak Spanish. MP2 says:

“So amo po ito sir language barrier po akon nakurian pero naka adjust man guihapon. Baman an ira culture nahibaru naman la ako makasakay ira kay iba man gud it ira culture” (MP2, Transcript 32, page 4-5, line 179-181).

(The language barrier, sir, is difficult for me to understand, but I will adjust and learn. About their culture, I learn to adapt to their culture, and their culture is very different.)

MP4 viewed is that:

“An language naman makuri an Spanish pero guin try namon mahibaro kay amo gud la it madali nga magkaintindihay kami it akon mga kaurusa kay Spanish man gud it ira language” (MP4, Transcript 53, page 11, line 409-412).

(“The language is Spanish, but we try to figure it out because it's so easy for us to understand and communicate if we know the language.”)

Our ability to connect with people is one of the most satisfying features of the human experience. It's a beautiful blessing to be able to communicate with someone in their language. In their personal and professional lives, bilinguals have the unique chance to speak with a broader spectrum of people. Knowing the language turns you into a local no matter where you go, practically and symbolically expanding your horizons. Communities will have an impact on you. The compassion of strangers will humble you. You will make friendships that will last a lifetime. And for these reasons alone, learning languages will pay off for many years to come (Lead with Languages, 2021).

4.2.7 Theme 3: Family is the Strength

4.2.8 Meaning:

According to David R. Mace (1985), “Nothing in the world could make human life happier than dramatically increasing the number of solid families.” The elements of a family's relationships that contribute to the family's emotional health and well-being are family strengths. Families that consider themselves vital frequently state that they love

each other, find living together fulfilling, and live in contentment and harmony. Professionals study families for a variety of reasons. But, perhaps, the most significant purpose is to assist us in learning to get along better with one another in what has been termed our most fundamental social institution and most intimate habitat (Encyclopedia.com 2021),

4.2.9. Evidence:

MP3 highlighted that when they arrived in America, they felt homesick, and they missed their family in the Philippines. Then they remember that they are in America only for OJT. MP3 said that:

“An adto nako ha America n aka feel man gud ako hin homesick Ireally miss my family in the first month then, but then I just remember that I am working here para ha ira, hira an nagiging strength nakon everyday pag natrabaho ako” (MP3, Transcript 42, page 7, line 279-282).

("When I was in America, I feel homesick. I miss my family in the first month then, but then I remember that I am working here for them; they become my strength every day when I work.")

Also MP4 reiterated and said that:

“Baman kun nakaka feel ako hin homesick siring pa normal naman la ito nao overcome ko man guihapon available man an internet natawag ako ha ira nag pa facebook kami tapos nawawara na it akon ka homesick”. (MP4, Transcript 52, page 11, line 406-409).

(If I can feel homesick, it's still normal, but I can overcome it; if the internet is available, I called them, and we were communicating on Facebook, and then I lost my homesickness.")

Further, DateMyAge.com, (2021), postulates that the strengths of a family serve as a basis for growth and positive change. Families become more potent when they focus on their strengths. The majority of families in the world are pretty strong. Without these characteristics, humans would not have survived for many generations. There are many more strong families in the world than there are dysfunctional families. We cannot afford to ignore this as a global human community.

4.3 On a piece of advice or guidance you want you want to share with the HM students.

4.3.1 Theme 1: Experiential Learning

4.3.2 Meaning:

Kent State University, (2021), highlighted that the process of learning through doing is known as experiential learning. Students can better apply ideas and knowledge taught in the classroom to real-world issues when they are engaged in hands-on experiences and reflection. Community work, service-learning, undergraduate research, study abroad/away, and culmination experiences such as internships, student teaching, and

capstone projects, to name a few examples, are all examples of experiential learning opportunities.

4.3.3 Evidence:

As one piece of advice, do not hesitate to have your on-the-job training abroad because you will learn a lot. MP3 pointed out that:

“It ako la masisiring sir kun mayda chance or opportunity nga parehas hin sugad ini ha amon tapos kaya it ira family nga magastusan hira ayaw hira pag alang kay damo talaga ira mababaruan kun adto na hira ha industry magagamit talaga nira ini pag adto na hira ha ira mga trabaho”(MP3, Transcript 45, page 8, line 300-304).

(“I can only say sir, if there is a chance or opportunity that is the same as ours and their family have enough money to spend for the expenses, don't let them hesitate because they will learn a lot especially if they are already in the industry)

MP2 also pointed out that:

“It akon la msisiring mas maupay mag ojt ha gawas labi na amerika kay damo iyo nababaruan kay nakakuha ka hin 1st hand experience ngan na ho hone an imo skills” (MP2, Transcript 33, page 5, line 190-192).

(“I'll just say it's more comfortable to work abroad, especially in America because you know a lot because you've gained 1st hand experience and you've honed your skills.”)

Furthermore, MP1 indicated that:

“Naging positibo ako sa pananaw ko simula ng Makapag America ako at marami akong na diskubre na marami pala akong kayang gawin” (MP1, Transcript 20, page 3, line 107-109).

(“I've been positive in my outlook since I came to America, and I've had a lot of discoveries that I can do a lot.”)

Furthermore (Kent State University, 2021) reported that students will benefit from experiential learning activities in the following ways: A better grasp of the course content; A broader perspective of the world and a sense of belonging Insight into their abilities, interests, passions, and values; Collaboration opportunities with a variety of organizations and persons; Professional skills and practices that are beneficial; The satisfaction of helping to meet community demands; and Self-assuredness and leadership abilities.

5. CONCLUSION

A university's well-framed and structured instructional program might be the foundation for a positive outcome for its students. Applying theoretical learning in the classroom is critical for particularly effective hospitality management training at Eastern Visayas State University. The students' on-the-job experiences in the United States of America were highlighted in this study.

According to the findings, on-the-job experiences have been beneficial and significant since they have received knowledge, abilities, and attitudes that apply to their future practice in the corporate sector. The essential learning they had, according to the trainees, was an awareness and knowledge of cultural differences between Americans and Filipinos in terms of corporate rules and practices.

This discussion demonstrates how crucial it is to have a robust on-the-job training program since it improves student learning results. As a result, solid corporate partnerships with organizations overseas have developed, promising future work prospects and increasing the employability of EVSU graduates. These narratives of students experiences are also part of every institution's, colleges, or university's benchmark for bringing their students into the world labor community, as they comply with international treaties and norms to which their country is a signatory. It improved student learning outcomes and established institutional links between the university and the worldwide market. This is in line with the university's thrusts and ambitions to internationalize the level of education available to its students. This is evidence of a successful program that will continue to support the university's goal of providing high-quality education.

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